

Reviewer guidance synthesis

Use of Résumé for Research and Innovation (R4RI)-like narrative CV: reviewer guidance synthesis

Purpose

Members of the [Joint Funders Group](#) have each developed guidance for reviewers (peer reviewers and panel/committee members) using an R4RI-like narrative CV format in their application process. This summary aims to highlight commonalities that may help in the development and implementation of your own guidance for reviewers.

Table 1: Summary of findings

Across a sample of four funders in January 2022 the following was observed:

Funder	Guidance accompanied by other resources	Location of applicant guidance	Training provided	Guidance tailored for different calls	Evaluation undertaken
1	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Reviewer guidance document → Reviewer forms 	No	No	Yes
2	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Reviewer form 	No	No	Yes
3	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Reviewer guidance document → Briefing video 	No	Yes	Yes
4	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Committee guidance document → Peer reviewer guidance document (in development) 	No	Yes	No

Synthesis of findings

Provision of guidance for reviewers

- All funders sampled are using an R4RI-like narrative CV in at least one funding opportunity and are providing guidance for reviewers to assess the CV. A number of other funders (not included within the table) are developing guidance.
- Three funders provide guidance within a reviewer guidance document, and two funders provide a reviewer form (a document completed by the reviewer containing their assessment).
- Two funders accompany their guidance with video resources they have developed. No funders indicated signposting to resources generated by others.

Training provided on the guidance

- Two funders are currently considering developing their training provision.

Tailoring reviewer guidance for different funding calls

- Two funders tailor their guidance for different funding calls; one noted that guidance was tailored based on different career stages for funding calls.

Evaluation

- Insights from evaluations undertaken by group members include the need for training and more detailed guidance on why a funder is using an R4RI-like narrative CV, and the principles of what a funder is trying to achieve in its use.

Common features and key considerations in developing guidance

- Funders have different motivations for implementing an R4RI-like narrative CV; it is helpful to be explicit to reviewers as to why your organisation is taking this assessment process.
- Ensure guidance is straightforward and not too long, and the process is streamlined.
- Steer reviewers to consider the information submitted in the R4RI-like narrative CV.
- The common features in the guidance have been pulled together in the [Developing guidance for reviewers – a starter guide](#) in the [Résumé Resources Library](#).

Next steps

- There is an aspiration to revisit the reviewer guidance synthesis with updated information in light of reviews and evaluations.

Version Number	Status	Revision Date	Author(s)	Summary of Changes
1.0	Complete	March 2022	Joint Funders Group	New resource created
2.0	Complete	May 2023	Joint Funders Group	Proof-edited and designed